

ECOBULK

Circular Approach for Eco-Composite Bulky Product

GA NUMBER: 730456

Project Website operative

Document Information

Report name	Project Website operative
Version number	1.0
Document number	D9.1
Due date for deliverable	31/08/2017
Actual submission date	30/11/2017
Lead beneficiary	ISWA

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 730456

Document Control page

Author	Jose Uribe
Version number	1.0
Date	30-11-2017
Modified by	
Comments	[instructions]
Status	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Delivered <input type="checkbox"/> Accepted
Action requested	<input type="checkbox"/> To be revised Deadline for action:

Revision History

Version	Date	Author/Reviewer	Notes
1.0	30-11-2017	Jose Uribe / ISWA	Final version

Executive Summary

This report will summarise the steps taken to design, build and fill with content a website for the ECOBULK project. The website is considered part of the Digital Communication and Dissemination task of the work package 9 for Communication and Dissemination.

The role of the website is twofold:

1. Serve as central focal point for information and digital communication materials for the public. It should make available any (public) project results, as well as inform visitors about the planned activities and give them the chance to contact and engage with the project wherever possible.
2. Serve as a central repository for private project documentation and provide the necessary structures that allow the partners in the consortium to share and their review their work, both in terms of general activities as well as deliverables.

With these two roles in mind, the website was divided into a private and public area.

The public area includes, among others, possibilities to write and display articles, incorporate newsfeeds from different sources, sign up for newsletters, display links for social media and sharing, partner profiles, a downloads section and a calendar of important dates events.

The private area includes more collaboration based functionality, with sections divided into work packages which include subsections for Tasks, Deliverables, Dates/Events, and a files section. There is also a shared files sections for the whole project, and a shared photo section.

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1. Introduction

1.1. Description of the document and pursue

The ECOBULK website has been considered in WP9 as one of the central elements for communication.

The site is 100% operational and accessible the registered domain ecobulk.eu.

The design of the website has been developed by ISWA with the collaboration of the consortium. This document presents a description of the website functionality, Look and Feel, and content development process.

1.2. WPs and Tasks related with the deliverable

The website is directly related to the Task 9.2 Digital Communications, but indirectly related to all Work Packages and Tasks since it serves both a repository and conduit for all project results to the general public.

2. Website Description

This chapter will give an overview of the website from a functional and design perspective.

2.1 Design

The public website design was based on a concept of simplicity and clean communication style. The colors and styles are based on and compatible with the identity set as designed by KNEIA, who was also responsible for the logo design.

Figure 1 ECOBULK public homepage

The private website design was based on a functional approach that enhances the ability to structure, find and track important content during the project. The layout places an emphasis on overviews and collects information to present at different aggregate levels.

Figure 2 ECOBULK private homepage

The project homepage is mainly dedicated to either easy navigation through the link structure, drop down context menus and a user customisable favourite links section.

The rest of the space is dedicated to an aggregate Recent Activities, which combines all activities throughout the website structure and allows users to see what is happening and where on the site.

There is also a section summary page, used to centralize the content for each separate Work Package section. This combines overviews of the different subsections with excerpts from the relevant dates, posted topics, the recently updated work package files, a list of tasks and a sidebar with recent activity aggregated from the different subsections.

The design for all sections and subsections follows the chosen high contrast, clean and structured layout philosophy that we believe enhances usability through simplicity and intuitiveness.

Work Package 9

NOV 26 - DEC 2 2017

DESCRIPTION

Communication and Dissemination Strategies

- To enable potential future exploitation of the results to their potential by disseminating the results to the relevant stakeholders.
- To ensure that the findings of the project are widely communicated to the public in general.
- To document undertaken and proposed dissemination and communication activities.
- To ensure the project results reach the relevant stakeholders who will use and implement them.
- To communicate the project and results to the general public.

RECENT ACTIVITY

TUESDAY, NOVEMBER 21

- Jose Uribe (Admin) updated D9.6: Massive Open Online Courses and other training materials 8:30pm
- Jose Uribe (Admin) updated Task 9.1 Dissemination and Communication Plan (M1-M48) 8:23pm
- Task 9.1 Dissemination and Communication Plan (M1-M48)

MONDAY, OCTOBER 30

- Jose Uribe (Admin) updated Task 9.2 Online Dissemination / Communication Activities (M1-M48) 3:04pm
- Task 9.2 Online Dissemination / Communication Activities (M1-M48)

THURSDAY, OCTOBER 19

- Jose Uribe (Admin) updated D9.6: Massive Open Online Courses and other training materials 3:14pm

TUESDAY, OCTOBER 10

- Jose Uribe (Admin) updated D9.6: Massive Open Online Courses and other training materials 8:10pm
- Jose Uribe (Admin) updated D9.2: Dissemination and Communication Plan 6:09pm
- Jose Uribe (Admin) updated D9.1: Project Website operative 6:06pm
- Jose Uribe (Admin) updated D9.3: Project newsletter 6:06pm
- Jose Uribe (Admin) updated D9.4: Final conference 6:06pm
- Jose Uribe (Admin) updated D9.5: Project video 6:06pm

THURSDAY, SEPTEMBER 21

- Jose Uribe (Admin) updated D9.6: Massive Open Online Courses and other training materials 3:07pm
- Jose Uribe (Admin) updated D9.6: Massive Open Online Courses and other training materials 3:05pm

TOPICS

TUESDAY, NOVEMBER 21

- Task 9.1 Dissemination and Communication Plan (M1-M48) By Jose Uribe (Admin) on August 3, 2017 - 3:39pm

MONDAY, OCTOBER 30

- Task 9.2 Online Dissemination / Communication Activities (M1-M48) By Jose Uribe on August 3, 2017 - 3:40pm

RECENTLY UPDATED FILES

- D9.5 - Project newsletter Oct 19 2017 - 6:06pm
- D9.4 - Final conference Oct 19 2017 - 6:06pm
- D9.5 - Project video Oct 19 2017 - 6:06pm
- D9.1 - Project Website operative Oct 19 2017 - 6:06pm
- D9.2 - Dissemination and Communication Plan Oct 19 2017 - 6:06pm
- D9.6 - Massive Open Online Courses and other training materials Nov 21 2017 - 6:30pm

TASKS

TASK	ASSIGNED TO	PRIORITY	TYPE	STATUS	COMMENTS	UPDATED
Task 9.1 Dissemination and Communication Plan (M1-M48)	Dominik Jasinski	Normal	Task	Open	1 / week 1 day ago	
Task 9.2 Online Dissemination / Communication Activities (M1-M48)	Dominik Jasinski	Normal	Task	Open	2 / month 7 hours ago	
Task 9.3 Offline Dissemination / Communication Activities (M1-M48)		Normal	Task	Open	3 / month 4 weeks ago	
Task 9.4 Production of Dissemination Materials (M1-M48)		Normal	Task	Open	3 / month 4 weeks ago	
Task 9.5 Training (M2-G-M48)	Jose Uribe	Normal	Task	Open	1 / month 1 week ago	

Figure 3 ECOBULK Work Package landing page

The whole site is designed to be responsive, so that it automatically scales content, navigation and the layout of blocks to best suit the different devices and native resolutions that could be used to access it.

2.2 Structure

The site map below shows the split between the public, private and different underlying sections of each.

Figure 4 ECOBULK Site Map

2.2.1 Public Site Navigation

The structure for the public is quite simple, with a landing page that branches out to the 5 functional areas:

Figure 5 ECOBULK Public Navigation Bar

1. About Ecobulk – A section for general information about the project.
2. Partner Profiles – A list of all the partners in the project with short descriptions, with the possibility of displaying any items related to that partner.
3. Calendar – A section to collect important dates and events of relevance to the public.
4. Downloads – A files section to house any public materials that should be made available to the public.
5. Partner Login – A link to the project section of the site for partners with an account.

2.2.1 Private Site Navigation

The private site is deeper since it tries to replicate/represent the project structure. The first level is the general project level, which is mostly an aggregate view of content from the work package sections.

Under the overview level, there are 9 work package sections that are reserved for work package specific content.

Figure 6 ECOBULK Project Navigation Bar

1. Project Dates – A section to aggregate important dates and events from each work package as well as from a general project level.
2. Project Deliverables – A section that aggregates all deliverables from across the 9 work package sections.
3. Project Files – A list of files of general use to the project, not directly related to a specific task or work package.
4. Project Photos – A collection of photos from project activities and related events that could be useful to the consortium members.

Figure 7 ECOBULK Work Package Navigation Bar

1. Work Package Calendar – A section to display important dates and events from the work package.
2. Work Package Deliverables – A section that lists all deliverables for the work package.

Figure 8 ECOBULK Work Package Deliverables

3. Work Package Files – A list of files of specific use to the work package.
4. Work Package Tasks – A list of tasks from project activities to help the work package members to organise their collaboration.

TASK	ASSIGNED TO	STATUS	COMMENTS	UPDATED
Task 9.1 Dissemination and Communication Plan (M1-M48)	Dominik Jasinski	Open	1	1 week 1 day ago
Task 9.2 Online Dissemination / Communication Activities (M1-M48)	Dominik Jasinski	Open	2	1 month 8 hours ago
Task 9.3 Offline Dissemination / Communication Activities (M1-M48)		Open	0	3 months 4 weeks ago
Task 9.4 Production of Dissemination Materials (M1-M48)		Open	0	3 months 4 weeks ago
Task 9.5. Training (M24-M48)	Jose Uribe	Open	0	2 months 1 week ago

RECENT ACTIVITY

TUESDAY, NOVEMBER 21

Jose Uribe (Admin) updated Task 9.1 Dissemination and Communication Plan (M1-M48) 6:23pm

Figure 9 ECOBULK Work Package Tasks

3. Functionality

Besides the normal functionality of posting and commenting on content, the website sections have had the following functions added for usability and convenience.

3.1 Public Site Functions

Carroussel – a standard image/item slider that allows multiple pieces of content to share the center stage on the home page.

Newsfeeds – a list of news items that are gathered from different sources and then curated to form a continuous stream of news items relevant to the project and its stakeholders.

Calendar – an overview of important, public, dates related to the project.

Files – a file repository functionality that allows standard file system tree structures to be created to store files available for downloads.

Social Media – links to social media accounts.

Newsletters signup – function to sign up for the 6-monthly newsletter for ECOBULK so that guests can follow the developments.

3.2 Private Site Functions

Groups

The private side of the website consists of a nested set of groups that allow the content to be segmented or restricted to certain groups. Each consortium member has its own group, and each work package section can contain these groups.

Events / Calendar

The Calendar collects and displays the important dates, selected from Events entries and the deliverables sections.

Figure 10 ECOBULK Event Calendar

Files

Files are treated as a special type of post, that has its own display mode that lists the entries in a traditional interactive file system tree structure, from which new files and folders can be easily created and arranged. The system distinguishes between files and documents, where a document is a file with surrounding meta-data, such as descriptions and can contain multiple multi-media sections.

Figure 11 ECOBULK File storage functionality

Tasks

Tasks are treated as a special type of post, that allows comments to change some of the settings in the original task to be able to assign and redirect tasks during collaboration.

Figure 12 ECOBULK Task list overview

The comments functionality for the tasks includes fields for:

1. Section – [ECOBULK SECTION] to redirect a task to a different section
2. Assigned to – [ECOBULK USER] to assign a person to work on the task
3. Status – [open|closed|pending] the current status of the task
4. Priority – [High|Low|Normal] to change the priority level
5. Type – [Task|Review] distinguishes task work and review work

The individual task item display is also customised with a small summary box which includes the task settings as described above.

All other standard functionality for posts applies with possibilities for attachments, notification lists, and revisions with comments.

Task 9.2 Online Dissemination / Communication Activities (M1-M48)
By Jose Uribe on Thursday, August 3 - 15:40pm

Leader: ISWA;
Participants: Oakdene Hollins, Knela.

This task will include the development of the project website, 2 professional video, social media sites, and project newsletter. The project website will be created in order to provide information and access to papers and any other nonconfidential documentation related to the ECOBULK project. The website will be operational as of Month 3 and will be the main information repository of the project, its objectives, results, the technology and all activities related to its developments/progress. KNEIA will contribute with material and inputs to the website, which will include a public and a private area, explained as follows:

- Public area: the first tool to disseminate information about ECOBULK. It will contain a general presentation of the project, its objectives, its outcomes, activities that can attract potential users and/or stakeholders, a description of the partners and a contact page, with links to relevant website on the matter.
- Private area: restricted to the partners and possible stakeholders who will approach the project during its implementation, since it will be the repository of all deliverables and confidential documents.

Besides the website, ISWA will be in charge of ECOBULK 6 monthly newsletter on the developments and implementation of the project. ISWA will produce at least 2 professional video. In addition, in order to spread ECOBULK projects' results, ISWA will manage the accounts of the 4 main social media platforms: Twitter, Facebook, Google+ and YouTube. A LinkedIn account will be created to disseminate the project's outcomes. Social media icons will be made available on the project website.

Attachments:
ecobulk_factsheet_m4_draft_v1.0.pdf
ecobulk_factsheet_m4_v1.2.pdf

Task Information
Section: WP9 Tasks
Assigned to: Dominik Jasinski
Status: Open
Priority: Normal
Type: Task
Submitted by Jose Uribe on August 3, 2017 - 3:40pm

UPDATES AND COMMENTS Expand All

By Jose Uribe (Admin) on September 20, 2017 - 12:35pm
Here is the first draft of the factsheet for the project. Since there is no result yet, we just present the goals and ambitions. The main

By Jose Uribe (Admin) on October 30, 2017 - 5:04pm
Updated the factsheet to reflect the input of the project leaders,

UPDATE TASK AND ADD NEW COMMENT

Task information

Section: WP9 Tasks
Assigned to: Dominik Jasinski
Status: Open
Priority: Normal
Type: Task

Task attachments

FILE INFORMATION	WEIGHT	OPERATIONS
ecobulk_factsheet_m4_draft_v1.0.pdf	0	Edit Remove
ecobulk_factsheet_m4_v1.2.pdf	1	Edit Remove

Attach media
Browse

Save

SECTION INFORMATION
WP9 Tasks

DOCUMENTS/MEDIA
ecobulk_factsheet_m4_draft_v1.0.pdf
ecobulk_factsheet_m4_v1.2.pdf

NOTIFICATIONS
Follow Follow to receive notifications.
Add groups, teams, or members to notifications

Jose Uribe (Admin)
Dominik Jasinski
Markku Vilkkilä
Ollivia Bertham
Enrico Mangino
Felipe Maya
Ruud Balkenende
Marco Grippa
Dolores Herrero
Cristina Barragan
Ciro Avollo
Oscar Ruiz
Juan Manzano
Jose Uribe

Do not send notifications for this update.

Figure 13 ECOBULK Task Item Details

Deliverables

Deliverables are treated as a special type of files, and are given the following functionality:

1. Define a (set of) deliverable date(s), which are then included in the dates overview.
2. Define a responsible partner (selection of 1 partner group)
3. Define a set of responsible partners (selection of multiple partner groups)

Figure 14 ECOBULK Deliverable Item Details

Photos

Photograph collections are treated as a special type of media post, with an extra display function that allows a thumbnail gallery per post.

Project Photos

This section is dedicated to photos taken throughout the project - at events, meetings, demonstrations etc.

RECENT PHOTO SETS

Kick-Off Meeting - TUDelft - Photos

PHOTO CONTENT

KICK-OFF MEETING - TUDELFT - PHOTOS

Pictures from the kick-off meeting in Delft, The Netherlands, 26th & 27th of June 2017.

Figure 15 ECOBULK Photo Item Overview

4. Content

The content for the site is planned to be developed as the project progresses. Both the structure and the necessary content will be regularly revised to fit the changing needs of the project. Currently the content consists of:

About ECOBULK – A brief description of the project, later to be expanded with:

1. Case Studies - Dedicated page to all industry case studies with links to relevant information, reports, graphics.
2. What are composite bulky materials? - Since this is the main subject of the project's research, we should have a page on it so when people search this phrase on Google, they will eventually land on our website.
3. Demonstrations – Will describe details of all planned demonstrations

News – Newsletters and articles based on the ECOBULK activities

Partner Profiles – A list of all the partners, which will be expanded to include also lists of their (public) contributions to the project.

Calendar – List of relevant events

Media – List of resources and downloads that will be expanded as they become available. This should eventually include:

1. Downloads - Logo, Graphics, Factsheets, etc
2. Reports - Used to host all reports in one place
3. Video Library - Collection of Videos published by ECOBULK
4. Press kit - Downloadable press brochure with all the key information about ECOBULK, quotes, zipped together with all logos